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*«ПОЧЕМУ?» – ЭТО ВОПРОС О КОТОРЫЙ ДО СИХ ПОР
РАЗБИВАЛАСЬ ВСЯ ЛОГИКА, ВСЯ ФИЛОСОФИЯ, ВСЯ НАУКА.*

ЭРИХ МАРИЯ РЕМАРК

**НАУЧНО-ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИЙ ИНСТИТУТ «ФИЗИКИ
РЕЗОНАНСНЫХ ЯДЕРНЫХ РЕАКЦИЙ» ЯВЛЯЕТСЯ НАУЧНЫМ
УЧРЕЖДЕНИЕМ, ОСУЩЕСТВЛЯЮЩИМ
ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ, ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ НАУЧНЫЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ РАЗРАБОТКИ В
ОБЛАСТИ НАУКИ, ТЕХНИКИ, КУЛЬТУРЫ И ПРОСВЕЩЕНИЯ.**

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TECHNOLOGIES FOR FORMING STUDENTS» SOCIALLY ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCE

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Abstract. Civic education is aimed at developing a person's civic competencies. The formation of socially active civic competencies includes a set of readiness and abilities that allow a person to actively, responsibly and effectively exercise the entire range of civil rights and obligations in a democratic society, to apply their knowledge and skills in practice.

The article highlights the issues of taking into account the constant political and legal relationship of students with a particular state, the mutual rights and obligations of the individual and the state, in the formation of students' socially active civic competence in the pedagogical process.

Keywords: Citizen, state, law, country, education, upbringing, attention, interest, service, justice, attitude.

Increasing the social activity of students in educational institutions, forming active civic competencies in them, and ensuring their place in social life and living as subjects of their own lives, are tasks that are of great importance today in terms of social and spiritual processes and relationships with society.

Many educational scientists consider socially active citizenship as a set of methods and procedures aimed at changing social conditions in accordance with needs, interests, goals and ideals, promoting and implementing social innovations, and forming the necessary social qualities in oneself [3]. Therefore, by developing active citizenship competencies in students, it is possible to form a sense of responsibility and involvement in the fate of the nation.

Citizenship is the legal connection of an individual with a particular state [12]. A person who has citizenship is called a citizen. This connection is

manifested in the rights and obligations of a citizen towards the relevant state and his protection by that state. According to Article 22 of the Constitution of Uzbekistan, a single citizenship is established throughout the territory of Uzbekistan [1] (a citizen of Karakalpakstan is also a citizen of Uzbekistan).

Citizenship is a permanent political and legal relationship of a person with a particular state; this relationship is expressed in the mutual rights and obligations of the person and the state. When a person acquires citizenship, the state recognizes all his rights and freedoms, takes measures to ensure their implementation. The state protects the interests of citizens, even when they are on the territory of other countries, and provides them with patronage. In turn, citizens unconditionally comply with the laws and regulations of the state, fulfill the obligations assigned to them. The set of these rights and obligations constitutes the political and legal status of a citizen, by which citizens are distinguished from foreign citizens and stateless persons.

The legal status of a citizen in Uzbekistan is specified in the Law «On Citizenship of the Republic of Uzbekistan» (March 13, 2020) [2]. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, citizenship defines a permanent political and legal relationship between an individual and the state, expressed in the set of mutual rights, obligations and responsibilities, and based on the recognition and respect for human dignity, fundamental rights and freedoms.

Active citizenship is a conscious participation of a person in the life of society, his conscious real actions (actions) in relation to the environment, reflected at the personal and social levels, aimed at the implementation of social values, a reasonable balance of personal and public interests. Today, every person must go through such a path in order to take a worthy place and become a citizen of his country.

Based on this definition, the signs of active citizenship can be considered as «the conscious choice of one's own efforts, the direction of activity aimed at changing the surrounding reality, associated with the interrelation of personal and public interests.» «A citizen is a conscious member of society, a person who subordinates his personal interests to the interests of the public.»

In the formation of students' socially active citizenship competence, three main components can be distinguished that make up the concept of «active civic position», which are patriotism, citizenship, and socio-political activism.

The active citizenship position is located in the range of socio-political relations and primarily reveals the subject's assessment of the events taking place in a particular area. The socially active position is focused on the ability to interact with society in order to change problematic situations.

There is a contradiction in constructing the concept of «socially active position», since the word position is a static state in a certain coordinate system, indicating the location of an object in relation to others, while the phrase social activity implies purposeful action in relation to society.

The socially active citizenship competence of students includes ethical, patriotic, and ecological components, but its unconditional implementation is a socially active activity. Active citizenship competence should be based on specific actions and activities in relation to the surrounding reality. Through active citizenship competence, the identity of a person is formed as a citizen and patriot of his country. In this case, a socially active position is the basis of citizenship education.

A socially active and civic position is a personal characteristic associated with an understanding of one's place and role in social relations, the ability to consciously and purposefully change the surrounding reality based on the uniqueness of the system of values of the individual and society.

are characterized by the degree to which a person mobilizes their internal resources (powers) to respond to social problems.

Technologies for the formation of students' socially active citizenship competences in the educational process are guided by the indicators specified in official state documents of the educational institution. Such a basic document includes the state educational standard.

The state educational standard is based on a systematic-activity approach aimed at the formation of a holistic, comprehensively developed personality, takes into account various parameters and comprehensive characteristics of the person receiving education, and assumes the continuity of educational means and results.

Based on the educational standard, our country is required to prepare graduates who are «socially active, respect law and order, measure their actions against spiritual and moral values, and understand their responsibility to their family, society, and homeland.»

The formation of socially active civic competence of students should reflect the upbringing of patriotism, respect for the Motherland, the past and present of the multinational people of the country; knowledge of one's own nationality, knowledge of the history, language, culture of one's people, the basics of the cultural heritage of one's region, country and the peoples of mankind; mastery of the humanistic, democratic and traditional values of a multinational society; upbringing of a sense of responsibility and duty to the Motherland.

Modern civic education is aimed at mastering the civic competencies of an individual. According to V.Sh. Maslennikova, civic competencies are a set of readiness and abilities that allow a person to actively, responsibly and effectively exercise the entire range of civil rights and obligations in a democratic society, to apply their knowledge and skills in practice [7].

individual parameters that can be interpreted as competencies in the pedagogical process, in particular, in the formation of a socially active and civic position, as well as a system for monitoring their mastery.

Competencies are formed in the process of education and upbringing, not only at school, but also under the influence of family, friends, work, politics, religion, culture, etc. Therefore, the formation of students' socially active citizenship competence depends on the entire educational and cultural situation in which the student lives and develops.

Education should model various competencies related to social activism and citizenship, which together create a holistic and functional personality. Thus, a socially active individual with a strong citizenship position should possess certain competencies.

Competencies are characteristics of knowledge, understanding and action. These characteristics should also be understood in the dimension of general abilities that are multifaceted, that is, those that go beyond the scope of specialization (general competencies), that are intellectual, social in nature and include the ability to self-manage (governance).

According to the European Qualifications Framework, the concept of competence includes:

- cognitive competence (knowledge as a concept), which includes the use of theories and concepts, as well as «tacit» knowledge acquired through practice;
- functional competence (skills and know-how), that is, what a person should be able to do in the field of work, education or social activity (knowledge as action);
- personal competence, which includes behavioral skills in a specific situation;
- ethical competence, which implies the presence of certain personal and professional values [4].

Cognitive competence includes knowledge of the history of one's country and region, the life path of creative individuals and heroes, symbolic information, basic knowledge of the state structure and constitution, knowledge of the infrastructure of civil relations (who is responsible for what) and the information system, the level of responsibility, cultural and natural heritage objects, and understanding the meaning of civic duty.

Functional competence is the ability of a person to act, to mobilize personal and, if necessary, other people's resources in carrying out his activities. For example, to be able to call rescue services in emergency situations, to interact with various structures to perform social tasks, to involve his peers in the activities of state structures, to help solve problems, and to use relevant modern information resources.

Personal competencies include patience, attention, curiosity, caring and showing interest, and respect for one's neighbor. This is also an integral part of civic education.

In terms of moral competencies, the student should understand social service, justice, the dignity and importance of the individual, the importance

of human relationships, honesty, as requirements of the code of ethics; the moral competence of the individual should be formed. Human life has its own value. Biophilia, based on love for living beings, allows a person to treat his neighbor with respect and tolerance, to respect his rights, to be a civilian who organically functions in the social and ecological environment, including a socially active and developing civic position, which allows not only to integrate into society, but also to change the social, cultural and ecological environment.

He can manifest himself in various aspects of life, without being limited to a particular direction. In the conditions of openness of social institutions, a student who has the above-mentioned set of competencies becomes an independent person who can successfully function in modern society. At the same time, it is important that he can use the acquired skills to develop himself as a person, the environment and society as a whole.

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